

Development Dynamics and Effects of NGOs on Livelihood a Case Study of Sanghar District

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Abstract:

the current research investigates development dynamics and effects of ngos' on livelihood a case study of Sanghar district. The main objective of this study was to furnish an all-inclusive strategical document as change agent for the Public Sector and NGOs as to increase percentage of successes in perspective of organizational implementations particularly for the most vulnerable and deprived peoples. non-governmental organizations. As various world studies show the results regarding poverty that forty percent worlds poverty resides in Asian countries. Government and NGOs imparted various projects and programs for uplifting the living status the peoples and that also have been improved but still required self-sufficiency in various areas, its core reason observed by the approached communities is poverty, that generates many other restraints in sustainable development. One of the major actors in socio-economic process is non-governmental organization. Although NGOs are considered by international agencies as alternate institutional structure or mechanism for transferring resources to themselves and to work for solving the problems at grassroot level. Hence southern countries take these entities for social transformation, economic advancement and strengthening democratic governance. The major issues in developing countries like Pakistan is to improve the livelihood of the poor people. As development partners, government has accepted existence of NGOs and their effective role in development related to specific segments and areas. The number and size of NGOs have swelled due to various reasons in the last decades especially in last quarter of the twentieth century. Therefore, it was an important period for assessment of NGOs' roles beyond of their motive and missions.

The purpose of this study is that NGOs are good institutional and operational options which intend to improve livelihood of the poor people in the context of Pakistan especially with the field results of District Sanghar. The research study is also depicted the review of the existing policies of NGOs and the improvement which was made in the livelihood of people amongst the target groups. Further, it works for improving the livelihoods in practices for replication as compared with public sector.

The study is combination of descriptive in nature and can be said that is mix method that applied for fulfilment of essential purpose . Ten NGOs were the part of the study, from which international were four and six were local with 40 and 60 ratios respectively.

Introduction: Glimpses on NGOs that are working in the study area and general features along with basic introduction and features of sample selected study area, that is also detailed out regarding the living conditions and demographic and geographic classification of the people or intensity of livelihood issues. This chapter also narrates the NGOs work, programs and their trickledown effect and impact to the deprived communities especially on their sustainable livelihood. Based on objectives and programs; the priorities settle down by the governing general bodies and board of directors of the institutes and managing personnel of the organizations. Except of many struggles with efficiency and efficacy, also occurring issues and solving mechanisms are the part of this chapter that discussed for the sustainable development of the community.

Keywords: *Development Dynamics, Effects of NGOS, Livelihood*

4.2 Historical Perspective of Development

The word development is described as an event constituting a new stage or phase in a changing situation. Development theories also known as the series of age-related changes that occurs with the passage of time. Various psychologists, including with Erikson, Jean Piaget, Lawrence Kohlberg and Sigmund Freud; all describe the development as series of stages.

Development theory is in fact a collection of theories about the desirable change or changes in society achieved in best way. Such theories draw on a variety of social science disciplines and approaches. Along with the passage of time, new experiences to generate new ideas and ways of advancement and growth as per need of the societies are becoming the part of development.

The NGO is an organization, on voluntary basis, calls it the group that serves the home-grown people for collective purposes and those are regional, national and international level and registered under the law of their estate; their lower limit and their funding level are at their own. A group of people to gather and to set collective beneficial bylaws and organized themselves with focussing them and registered the group under settled any rule by the State; organizing group may be voluntary citizen or rural, local, national or an international level but existing depends on the collective benefit of all and not for the purpose of any one individual. These organizations carry out a diversity of services and humanitarian functions, basically they play role of approaching the segment of peoples that left behind by the government because of various reasons and the NGO role is bridge between state and communities; with basic motive to develop the deprived communities and assisting them in sustainable uplifting.

According to Hall. J, 2006; NGOs always follow public and common peoples' agendas and can be defined as social interest entity for public except of business or commercial purpose.

In 610 Hazrat Muhammad PBUH started preaching the message of Islam, he continued it even though many opposed him, but he never stopped it and continued without thinking of any reward or return.

Islam also teaches charity and so many teachings of helping the others; like rights of neighbor, zakat (right of the poor), care about humanity, no any discrimination on basis of belief. These are the clear and concise examples of NGOs' objectives.

As today, it is known that the NGOs emerged because of famine¹ and war, this concept was found in the caliphate of Hazrat Umar; he ensured adequate relief to all peoples and said that no one should sleep hungry in the night-time in his governance. Often, he used to walk; disguising himself especially at night-time, basic purpose of that was facilitating the needy people that have been neglected by state and assessing himself that what people expecting from him; either his governing policies are human friendly or not.

1.2 Background

The concept of NGOs is found from the beginning of mankind however the existing history is very old and dates back about 1807 to the abolition of the Britian slave trade², in beginning many voluntary groups has been formed and organized in shape of small or large organizations based on non-for-profit activities and prioritizing social and communal interests; the basic purpose was to address the issues of slavery. In that period, one could witness the founding of today's world major NGOs, many followed post-war reconstruction. In sixties NGOs brought the confrontational approaches³ and addressed the issues of war and famine, but they started to make attention to their grass root causes through lobbying and campaign. Various international organizations like MSF, Christian Aid, Oxfam Novib, Unicef and Amnesty International "AI" collectively started criticism on the government began to reform or critic the states regarding strategical reforms and policies should be included in priorities of the current ruling governments. Polygonal organizations brought various ideas and unfold them accordingly. Till 1990's the international humanitarian NGOs' prime role remained same till now. This providing compassionate assistance and protection on the outskirts of violent conflicts evolved and changed significantly.

¹ Famine: Famine is known as severe shortage of Food, usually caused by crop failure and disaster.

² Slave Trade: The procuring, transporting, and selling of human beings

³ Confrontational Approach: The Approach based on overall concerns or said to be More moderate approach.

There was positive recognition to NGOs both in developed and developing countries. They recognized them as “potential forces for social and economic development”; socioeconomic development always plays vital role in entire development process. In the beginning NGOs role was limited to ‘care and welfare’ or ‘philanthropy’ but nowadays NGOs considered an organized force that brings structural changes⁴ in the society. NGOs have set their goals for transformation of existing structures, strengthening democratic values and processes and awareness among the society. The growing disenchantment with institutionalized welfare which started in the late 1960s has received momentum from bilateral national development. First can be said that the oil crisis in the entire world has caused a lot of problems and the recently ruling governments been forced to save the institutes and lives of their common people and institutions but social development seemed to have come to an end. The other side of the bilateral development during 1980s and nineties was to reduce the distances and make the world to one village ideology with also decreasing the powers and meeting the needs of social development. But, the growing importance of NGOs in developing countries also deals with new social, economic, political and environmental concerns, which means becoming active in ‘awareness-raising’, social organization, and in advocating change to the status quo⁵.

Associations, organizations and groups are formed independently in the democratic societies for the betterment and development of locality. This exercise produces the space for the formation of independent associations and organizations. The word NGO came into being first time with the creation of United Nation. The UN, also as an inter-governmental organization, made it possible for certain approved international non-state agencies i.e. non-governmental organizations to be awarded or observer status at its assemblies and some of its meetings. Later, the term was used widely, according to the UN, any kind of private organization that is independent from government control can be termed as an NGO, that will be free from profit, crime and politics.

Literature Review

Netting, R. M., Wilk, R.R, & Arnould, E.J. (Eds.). (1984) argue, “household” means shared dwelling place where one can live and cooperate with all members especially play part in money earning; one’s physical appearance is not matter but monetary contribution can matter as overall, despite of their physical absence at household and to contribute to domestic revenue through their remittances⁶.

During 1989; Chambers argues that it can’t be said that susceptibility is owing to dearth of ones want, nevertheless frailty, insecurity, and acquaintance risks, threats, shocks and stress.

Schwartz & Clay (2000) support the idea that in the world various types social organizations are working for human being but rudimentary and core unit is household where one is supported initially morally and financially in setting the future direction and currently enlarging the everyday life for wider level with the passage of time. According to Schwartz and Clay household is a place where one born, grow and adopting social norms, values, strength, freedom and distinction at all levels.

Singh (1992), pointing the NGOs operating and management mechanism especially setting working priorities and heavily relying on donor or external funding for operations and restraint in open membership. Not only this but sector’s contribution in socio-economic growth is also questionable in the country, because mostly their SOPs focussing on freedom in operations except of considering the bylaws of state.

Vivian, J., & Maseko, G. (1994) observes several

NGOs projects varies as per geographic priorities for example in developing countries focussed projects related to addressing the environmental issues except of livelihood, microcredit or others. Based on the research considering the NGOs working variety of projects in with advanced nations, far-flung areas, deprived peoples, urban and rural; concluded as diversity of exposures in delivering suggesting one thing that is NGOs involvement directing the sustainable development. Now; Asian countries also considering the NGOs involvement positive and assisting for the governments but their working mechanism with organizations still in review process for policy finalization in social contexts.

⁴ Structural Changes: Changes can be initiated by policy decisions or lasting changes in resources, population or society.

⁵ Status quo: The Current political or social conditions.

⁶ Remittance: Often used migrants regarding to transfer money to their home country.

Davis, Canon., T, and P. Blaikie., during 1994 explaining the term vulnerability as the strength of characteristics of an individual or a group to utilize during to cope or the response in facing the disaster or to recover that may natural, human made hazards⁷ or disasters.

Vijay, M. (1994) examines the capacity building institutes and organizational role in developing of progressive programs regarding to enhance productivity and performance. He suggested by his study that to give priority to the capacity building of Non-Governmental Organizations that are involved in enhancing the capacity through trainings and learned exposure in revelations.

Lewis, D. E (1994) studied the nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) maintains that NGOs have been attempting to redefine their role in the context of state and civil society to contribute substantively to the regional development strategies. Their role often cantered on both political and economic priorities, in contrast with the international NGOs, which tend to stress their political character and to define Third World requirements in terms of economic rather than political necessities. This means a rethinking of the relationship with the state, promoting a debate between NGOs concerning the question of how NGOs parallel to work with the state.

Hudock, A. C (1995) geographic and demographic⁸ variations impact on the results of the organizations that quoted with diverse examples in different situations. For this purpose, Southern or Northern NGOs to face many problems during the implementation of the programs in the field. Suggestions and results of the Gambia and Sierra Leone study discussed; she said that in both countries Southern not profit organizations performed their functions in delivering the projects depending on Northern in perspective of funds and monetary assistance. Dependency always creates uncertainty in service provider as well as in end user or beneficiaries especially during the completion of funding cycle, because of this long-term planning is too difficult and doubt always creates bi problems and affects the efficiency. Not only timeline is the issue, but other external and internal forces can be expected to disturb partially or entirely to the programs, for example civil war, inflation, poor relationship with recent ruling party of the country results on policy. Northern organizations required to avoid the difficulties because of unstable and unreliable situations regarding to stop the running projects in fields in both countries and make policy on to continue funding at any cost for the agreed projects for timeline.

Data Collection Methodology

This Research Study is designed to assess socioeconomic impact of NGOs on livelihood of people specifically in Sanghar district, study conducted with those beneficiaries that have been benefited by the NGOs specially in livelihood projects. For this purpose, two types of data sources have been used. Secondary data has been gathered from literature review, reports, articles, journals, organizational PCRS, QPRs, MPRs⁹, donors and government reports, Development Statistics reports.

Results

Figure 4.1: Three Ways of Relationship Human and Economic Development

⁷ Human Hazards: Human adversary actions such as threatened, chemical attack or likewise acts losses the peoples.

⁸ Demographic Variations: study of statistics such as birth, deaths, income, and incidences which illustrate the changing

⁹ PCRS: Mostly project closure reports but this can be exercised in monthly or quarterly 'three months' progress reports of activities against target or plan.

Source: Eur J Nutr; May-2017 (Optimal nutrition and the ever- changing dietary landscape)

After analyzing the existing capitalistic growth-development theoretical apparatus, introduces the new model which integrates the variables of freedom, democracy and human rights into the existing models and argue that any future economic growth-development of any nation depends on this emerging model as it witnesses the third wave of unfolding demand for democracy. Because of this the knowledge sector added in growth theories with two new concepts of 'micro knowledge' and 'macro knowledge'¹⁰. Micro knowledge depends on what one learns from school or from various existing knowledge providing sources and macro knowledge is the essential philosophical thinking of a nation that all receive inherently.

Using these ideas, Rostow confined his classic "Stages of Economic Growth" during 1960, which shows five steps on which all countries categorized as developed and underdeveloped as; I. Traditional Society II. Pre-condition to take-off. III. Take-Off IV. Drive to maturity V. High mass consumption.

4.4 Development and NGOs

NGOs have distinct place in economic development, especially in developing countries. They provide services to society through welfare works for community development with their own way, assistance in national disasters, sustainable system development considering hot and burning issues and popular movements. It all happens with the involvement of localities beyond the level of involvement and this is the main difference among public sector and NGOs.

Nowadays Non-Governmental Organizations or NGOs became an extensively theme in the third world countries as well vastly known as social business¹¹. The NGOs have appeared as the assisting source for many people without food, cloth, education and basic health facilities directly and indirectly many of them provided employment opportunities. Best one example in the world is Bangladesh that is one of the top thirteen poor countries. NGOs in Bangladesh continued playing the role to develop it and significant role in the attainment of sustainable economic growth and development.

In a short overview, we turn a consequence, that the NGOs are attracting increased attention and recognition among academics and practitioners of development and development assistance. Many researchers support NGOs' activities because of their approaching to remote or far-flung communities for their efficiency and low cost of operations e.g., micro-credit programs (Mask, 1995; Hulme & Moseley, 1996; USAID, 1996), their promotion of sustainable system development (Korten, 1990; Smillie, 1995), and their potential role for organizing and representative bodies in civil societies (Brown and Korten, 1991; Carroll, 1992). The rapid growth of NGOs is also been seen because of governments' failure to alleviate poverty or intricate process of public sector, various levels of bureaucracy involvement in corruption and a lack of accountability of government (Booth, 1994; Fisher, 1998; Nelson, 1995; Clarke, 1998, Lewis, 2015).

There are many visible indicators of this difference, one has been the devotion of energy and resources by companies to environmental and social affairs¹². Companies are taking responsibility for their externalities and documenting the impact of their activities on a range of stakeholders individually and collectively. Staff voluntarism and continuation of the struggle with patriot of voluntarism.

Some groups may pursue a single objective policy¹³ - for example access to AIDS drugs in developing countries or press freedom. Others will pursue more sweeping policy goals such as poverty eradication or humanitarian rights protection.

¹⁰ Micro knowledge' and Macro knowledge: These are the types of project knowledge and micro-knowledge, needed for performing a single task and macro-knowledge, all the knowledge possessed by people from a given organizational means larger scale.

¹¹ Social Business: Business that has specific social objectives, the investors/owners can gradually recover the money invested but cannot take any dividend beyond that point.

¹² Social Affairs: Social gathering regarding carryout communal task or gathering for the purpose of promoting fellowship.

¹³ Single objective policy: To formulate specific objective-based policy, for example here is about to eradicate AIDS. It is often research based objective followed policy.

Public surveys reveal that NGOs often enjoy a high degree of public trust, which can make them a useful, not necessary always.

Some NGOs prefer to remain at a distance, by monitoring, publicizing, and criticizing in cases where companies fail to take seriously their impacts upon the wider community as they projected. It is concluded that Prahalad & Hart, 2010; according to KPMG report, that government has four distinct roles in addressing sustainability concerns. These roles are as following.

The role of Public Sector is categorized as subsequent.

- I. Policy development
- II. Regulation
- III. Facilitation
- IV. Internal Sustainability management

4.5 NGOs in the World

There are diverse organization are working in the various areas of the development that may be for non-profit as prioritized for the development of deprived people of the poor segment of the community Eg. American Civil Liberties Union Foundation, Global Giving, Equal Justice Initiative, International Rescue Committee, Plan International, Save the Children, Oxfam and some of them for profit organizations, profit organizations also categorized as profitable corporations, limited companies means purely are doing business for earning and few are working for some return but with concept to develop the poor and deprived communities and best example of such organizations is microcredit providing institutes or organizations as ASA from Bangladesh, PPAF from Pakistan, Consumer Credit Union “Economic Partnership”¹⁴ from Russia, Saadhana Microfin Society from India, Kashf Foundation from Pakistan.

Leading Organizations in the world is given in the subsequent 4.2 table along with working area or origin.

Table 4.2: Leading NGOs in the World

S/no	Name of NGO	Working area/origin	S/no	Name of NGO	Working area/origin
1	BRAC	(Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee)- Bangladesh, Microcredit and livelihood.	11	Apopo	(Tanzania), training and Capacity Building as mine detectors, to detect tuberculosis in human
2	Wikimedia Foundation	(United States), information disseminating	12	Root Capital	(US), \$460 million in loans to sustainable enterprises in Africa and Latin America, reaching 2.6 million people in poor
3	Acumen Fund	(New York-based), \$81 million investments in 72 countries worldwide.	13	Handicap International	(France)- Over 60 countries crucial assistance
4	Danish Refugee council	(Denmark) 35 countries & more than 1.5 million people	14	IRC (International Resource Committee)-	Emergency relief, rehab. over 40 countries
5	Partners in Health	(United States) pre-eminent public health NGO globally	15	Barefoot College	(India)- has nurture a form of grassroots social entrepreneurship
6	Ceres	(Boston-based-managed to lead a climate change & water scarcity)	16	Landesa	(US), secure land rights for the world's poorest people
7	CARE International	(Switzerland)-Fight against global poverty-87 countries	17	Ashoka	(US), over 3,000 fellows in more than 70 countries.
8	Medicines Sans Frontiers	(Switzerland)- 68 countries, close to 32,000 staff.	18	One Acre Fund	(Kenya), to serve over 130,000 farming families

¹⁴ Economic partnership: Mostly used in economic interests’ partnership intensive alliances, signed by two or more countries, that provide for reciprocal *economic* integration and participation, that may between two or more parties.

9	Cure Violence (US)-	(US)-(formerly Cease Fire) focused on addressing challenge	19	Clinton Health Access Initiative	(US)-HIV/AIDS resulting in more than \$1 billion
10	Mercy Corps	(US), Portland but active in over 41 countries, using 3R programs	20	Heifer International	(US)- 15.5 million families helped in more than 125 countries

Source: Wikipedia and NGOs documentaries- 2016

This is the scenario of the NGOs working at the world level which are involved in the development of deprived and non-developed areas.

4.5.1 Leading NGOs Working in Pakistan

As we discussed regarding the leading NGOs in the world earlier, but many organizations also are working in Paksitan. Profit and for Non-profit Organizations are working parallel with public sector, but research study focussed the non-for-profit organizations. In Pakistan international and national organizations are involved in uplifting the poor peoples, some organizations are as; Aman Foundation, Action Aid, Plan International, ACTED, Oxfam Novib, PPAF, NRSP, Aurat Foundation etc. Subsequent 4.3 table is given for showing working priority with year of establishment.

Table 4.3: NGOs’ Establishment Year with Focused Working Area

S/no	NGO	Year of estab.	Working profile/Area of interest	S/no	NGO	Year of estab.	Working profile/Area of interest
1	Ahung	1995	Health and Craft	19	Health Education and Literacy Trust	1994	Its name showing its working; formal as well informal.
2	Adult Basic Education Society (ABES)	1972	Education- Formal/Nonformal	20	HANDS		
3	AKHS	1924	Physical infrastructure and health related programs	21	Kashf Foundation	1996	Microcredit
4	APWA	1965	Social & Monetary Welfare	22	Marie Stopes Society	1990	Reproductive Health
5	ACE (Association of Creation of Employment)	1997	Monetary and Financial Wellbeing	23	MCWA of Pakistan	1961	Reproductive Health
6	Banh Bei	1987	Education & Health	24	National Rural Support Program	1991	Socioeconomic Development
7	Bedari	1992	Psychological Welfare	25	PFBPW (Pakistan Fed. Of Bus. And Professional Women)	1954	Advocacy
8	Behbud Association	1979	Health & Education	26	Pakistan Foundation Fighting Blindness	1988	physically challenged
9	Bunyard literacy community Council	1994	Women's Empowerment	27	Pakistan Women Lawyers Association	1981	Legal Services to women
10	De LGW Program	1988	Technical and soft trainings	28	Sungi Dev. Foundation	1989	Mobilization with deprived communities
11	Family Planning Association of Pakistan	1953	Health	29	Aurat Publication and Information Service Foundation	1986	Women Empowerment
12	RAHMA Islamic Relief Pakistan	1999	Economic Development	30	Shirkat Gah- Women's Resource Centre	1975	women's ng, income generating development
13	PFFB - Pakistan Foundation Fighting Blindness	1988	Services for visual impaired	31	Aurat Foundation	1986	deals with a wide spectrum of women's welfare
14	Sustainable Development Policy Institute	1992	Wellbeing, within and across generations	32	Disaster Preparedness and Response Team (DPART)	2005	Emergencies act as volunteer disaster workers
15	Human Rights Commission of Pakistan	1986	Human Rights	33	Edhi Foundation	1951	Medical care, emergency & burial services and welfare
16	Citizen's Commission for Human	1985	Human and civic ecology and sustainability	34	Fauji Foundation	1954	Social protection programs

17	The Network for Consumer Protection	1992	independent information about goods and services	35	FIDA	2004	Relief & rehabilitation, and sustainable development.
18	Institute of Rural Management	1995	Capacity building of rural communities	36	Jaago Pakistan	2003	Awareness against social evils such

Source: NGOs directory- 20017-18

Table 4.3 explains the establishment year of the organization and its working priority sector that they are working in Pakistan.

4.5.2 Non-Governmental Organizations in Sindh

Although there are various organizations are working in Sindh or registered under any legal registering authority as per Government Policy. Dissertation already contained information regarding mainly organizations mainly working at world level and Pakistan along establishment and working priorities; the subsequent table explains the leading local organizations which are working in Sindh especially in development sector along with their existence, preferred working interest and especially in livelihood with interest intensity. Table 4.4 showing the list of organizations which are playing positive role in development especially in livelihood of peoples.

Table 4.4: Non-Governmental Organizations in Sindh

S/no	Name of Organization	Working since with	S/no	Name of Organization	Working sine with
1	SAFWCO	Working since 1996, Working with PPAF, Oxfam GB and P& D on livelihood-Sanghar	9	Banh Beli	To encourage coordination and livelihood initiatives in the specific area.
2	SCOPE	Working since 2001 on environment and livelihood	10	TRDP	To work on institutionalization and socioeconomic development-Sanghar
3	NRSP	Working on livelihood, Socioeconomic Development	11	AKPBs	To work on infrastructure, livelihood and development since 1980
4	SRSO	Since 1984 on development and for poverty alleviation	12	RWF	Since 2002 empowerment of vulnerable and marginalized groups-Sanghar
5	HANDS	Since 1979, in Helath, DRR and livelihood-Sanghar	13	RDF	to support local indigenous institutions & on livelihood-Sanghar
6	Pakistan Fisher Folk Forum	Working on indigenous fisher communities' livelihood -Sanghar	14	IET	Integrated Development Indigenous Housing Systems and livelihood since 2000.
7	BRDS	Since 1995 on Economic development and livelihood of ultra-poor	15	SRSP	Since 1995 to promote sustainable development & to reduce the poverty
8	SPO	working since 1994 to strengthen and support community organizations; advocacy and livelihood.	16	(SDSC)	Since 1994 working of socio-economic improvement in backward regions of Sindh.

Source: Organizational Bulletin and NGO directory-2017

Above mentioned in 4.4 table organizations are those institutes which are working for the people of the deprived societies even though various other organizations are in the Sindh that are working for the sake of name or grabbing the resources¹⁵ or playing middle role in the community for implementing the other organizations program.

4.5.3 NGOs Working in Sample Study Area

Already discussed and given summarized tables of working organizations lists accordingly, World, Pakistan and Sindh Province now here are the organizations are in the study or sample area of the research. I. Sustainable Development Foundation II. Sindh Agricultural & Forestry Workers Coordinating Organization (SAFWCO) III. Pakistan Fisherfolk Forum IV. Marie Stopes Society V. SEDA VI. Women Welfare

¹⁵ Grabbing the resources: Here it refers to NGOs working for the sake of taking resources except of community development or those actors who wants to access to or control over *resources grabbed* from various sources.

Association (WWA) VII. Thardeep VIII. Shirkat Gah IX. RDD X. ACTED XI. Aware XII. ASA Foundation. XIII SSF.

Now the subsequent 4.1 chart is giving detail of voluntary organizations beyond their capacity of their working but as per social welfare department facts and figures are as;

Graph 4.1: Taluka Wise Official Numbers of Organizations in Study Area

Source: Social Welfare Department -Sanghar- 2017-18

Above Graph 4.1 shows status of voluntary organizations which are registered under social welfare department; as per their report total 419 voluntary organizations are working there & out of that 153 are inactive voluntary organizations means their role in development is nothing but remaining 266 voluntary organizations are working and they are involved in uplifting of poor community or segment of the society directly or indirectly with leveraging the funds from other institutes.

Cited organizations are those registered groups which are working in study area and implemented few or a few projects in the district but so many other institutes which are working in Sanghar district came into being under some specific purpose as for the development of their area or crowding funds at local level; mentioned groups as below may community organizations, villages organizations, local support organizations, common interest groups, farmer organizations.

Graph 4.2: Union Council Based Networks of Local Organizations

Source: SAFWCO progress report-2017-18

Graph 4.2 explains the total geographical coverage under the network of local organizations at union council level; total UCS are 55 out of which 21.8 percentage is organized means they are recorded in accordance with the law Social Department.

Very glad to see during the field what an interesting work doing well by the organizations with participation of local people and what behavioural changing activities done by them.

4.6 Role of NGOs in District Sanghar

According to the people in the study area; organizations have done little but different and productive work in surrounding, so many villages, villagers uplift themselves in the various development areas for example education, access of and to PWDS¹⁶, qualitative education, small loans or grants for uplifting the poor to non-poor.

NGOs also play significant role in the identification of livelihood problems of the local communities and deprived households; it all happened with the involvement of the native dwellers¹⁷ based on national & international parameters after validation of community perspective indicators of the locality.

Subsequent areas are given which shows clearly the impact or performance of the NGOs.

Graph 4.3: Roads' Infrastructure in Sindh and Sample Research Study Area

Source: 1. Statistics and Development 2004 -2018
2. NGOs progress reports-2017-18

Graph 4.3 Shows the roads infrastructure last five years with high and low type of roads and NGO community-based networking or link roads with main or central roads.

Graph 4.3 explains that at Sindh level 6713 roads falls in low category except of improving in 2013 as compare to 2012 and in Sanghar remain same 50 as compared to last year; also, NGO shows with change of 10 as compared to previous year. In next year 2014 at Sindh level positive change is observed that is 7875 as with previous 2013 year and Sanghar shows no change and remains stability stagnant with same number 50 and NGO also shows comparative change occurs as change observed as 20 and year 2015 explains as the slower change but in positive direction at province level; 880 and in study area comparative with previous years is only 11 and NGO explains as number decreased as because of Public sector policies' rigidity and the progress was remained -18 as compared to previous year but still in positive. Year 2016 shows high level in upward direct at Sindh as comparative to 2015 the number is 1320 and in sample area it falls comparatively the number is -246 means the number is too slower and NGO number is decreases that is -12 and it all because of SOPs¹⁸ of public sector for the organizations and there observed less interest. Graph 4.4 shows different sectors contribution in study area.

¹⁶ PWDs: it refers to Persons with disabilities, as per UN those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments is known as PWDs. Or those who could not perform in the society on equal basis as compare to normal peoples.

¹⁷ Native dwellers: Local inhabitants of place, originally habitant of the specific area known as native dwellers.

Graph 4.4 Sectoral Contributions in Livelihood of Study Area

Source: Statistics Development 2004-2018 & Non-profit organizations reports.

Graph 4.4 explains the share of livelihood of various sectors in the population of study area. This explains the most topper share is paid by the livestock which is 46.006 percentage and second one is Agriculture which is 25.726 percentage of whole and industry sector paid 12.334 percentage and Health 0.155 percentage of population and education contributes 2.013 percentage in means of living to the people of the study area; mixed various sectors share is 12.365 percentage and NGO also contributes in Sanghar and its % is 3.401; this is comparatively higher.

Conclusions

The first and most important requirement is to meet the first objective for the research is 350 direct household beneficiaries and 50 NGO representative were enquired to explain the approximate level of addressing the livelihood problems of the people for the period of last one and half (2003 to 2018). Cross tabulation¹⁹ been placed to meet analytical data and exploratory research, also different reviews have been accorded again and again as the provided statistics should be better and reliable. The data is given in the following graphs; tables, and charts. Subsequent graph 4.5 shows the NGO performance frequency as per response of the livelihood beneficiaries.

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